

THE ROLE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: In modern society, the role of foreign languages is increasing. Knowledge of a foreign language gives young people the opportunity to join the world culture, use the potential of the vast resources of the global Internet in their activities, as well as work with information and communication technologies and multimedia teaching aids.

Key words: Foreign language, communicative activity, modern society, Knowledge, information, communication technologies, Internet, multimedia, teaching aids

The purpose of teaching a foreign language is the communicative activity of students, that is, the practical knowledge of a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to activate the activity of each student in the learning process, to create situations for their creative activity. The main goal of teaching a foreign language to secondary school students is to educate a person who is willing and able to communicate, people who are willing and able to receive self-education. Participation in various international programs, the opportunity to study abroad implies not only a high level of foreign language proficiency, but also certain personality traits: sociability, lack of a language barrier, knowledge of international etiquette, a broad outlook, the ability to what is called “present” oneself. As a rule, when performing various tests when entering a higher educational institution or participating in competitions and olympiads, a strict time limit for completing each task is set at the USE, which requires a special type of preparation. To achieve all these goals, of course, effective assistance to the teacher is provided by the use of computer technology and Internet resources in teaching English, presentations.

The computer, in our time, is a very important and independent thing. Many children and even adults use it only to play computer games. But, fortunately, there are many who have found the right use for it. So, for example, he helps in his studies. It is very convenient when such an assistant is at hand, because we can print abstracts, reports, in a word, everything we need without leaving home. In addition, a computer can help in learning a foreign language. After all, there are a lot of disks, electronic textbooks, multimedia training programs that lead to good results in learning English. Therefore, I determined the purpose of my work: to reveal the role of a computer and software in the successful mastery of the English language. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- to show the role of the computer in the modern communicative technology of teaching foreign languages,
- to reveal the variety of forms of using a computer and software in the successful mastery of the English language, the use of Internet information resources, the creation of computer presentations in English.

The role of the computer in modern communicative technology of teaching foreign languages

At present, the introduction of a personal computer, multimedia technology and the global information computer network Internet affects the education system, causing significant changes in the content and methods of teaching foreign languages. The modern teacher faces the problem of finding a new pedagogical tool. In my teaching activities, I came to the conclusion that in modern conditions, given the great and serious interest of students in information technology, this opportunity can be used as a powerful tool for developing motivation in English lessons.

The computer allows you to qualitatively change the control over the activities of students, while providing flexibility in managing the educational process. The role of the teacher is equally important here. He selects computer programs for the lesson, didactic material and individual tasks, helps students in

the process of work, evaluates their knowledge and development. The use of computer technology makes and allows an informed choice of the best training option.

The use of a computer as a tool for working with information is very diverse and diverse. He can look through the electronic library in a few seconds and find the required information. When using a computer, verbal communicative activity should be considered in three aspects. Firstly, as free communication of students in real time through the use of e-mail and information networks, that is, as an authentic dialogue in writing between communication partners. Secondly, as an interactive dialogue interaction between the student and the computer, in which the real goals of communication are pursued, that is, as a human-machine dialogue. Thirdly, as the communication of students in the classroom in the process of working with computer training programs that act as a stimulus for communication and a means of recreating the conditions of the communication situation.

The specificity of the subject of a foreign language determines the active and appropriate use of the computer in the classroom. The leading component of the content of teaching a foreign language is teaching various types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, writing. A training computer program is a simulator that organizes the student's independent work, manages it and creates conditions under which students independently form their knowledge, which is especially valuable, because knowledge obtained in finished form is very often past their consciousness and does not remain in memory. The use of computers in English lessons is the need of the time.

The use of computer technology in English lessons.

In recent years, the question of the use of new information technologies has been increasingly raised. These are not only modern technical means, but also new forms of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. The use of multimedia tools helps to implement a student-centered approach to learning, provides individualization and differentiation, taking into account the characteristics of

children, their level of learning, inclinations. Learning English with the help of computer programs is of great interest to students.

Disks that exist today allow displaying information on a computer screen in the form of text, sound, video, and games. Learning with the help of a computer makes it possible to organize the independent work of each student. Integrating a regular lesson with a computer allows the teacher to transfer part of his work to the computer, while making the learning process more interesting and intense. At the same time, the computer does not replace the teacher, but only complements it. The selection of training programs depends, first of all, on the current educational material, the level of training of the trainees and their abilities.

Working with a computer not only contributes to an increase in interest in learning, but also makes it possible to regulate the presentation of educational tasks according to the degree of difficulty, encouraging correct decisions. In addition, the computer allows you to completely eliminate one of the most important causes of a negative attitude to learning - failure due to a lack of understanding of the material or a problem in knowledge. It is this aspect that is provided by the authors of many computer training programs. The student is given the opportunity to use various reference manuals and dictionaries that can be called up on the screen with a single click on the mouse. Working on a computer, the student gets the opportunity to complete the solution of the problem, relying on the necessary help.

Significant progress in the development of personal computers and computer technologies leads to changes in the process of teaching foreign languages. The active and appropriate use of a computer in an English lesson seems possible and appropriate based on the specifics of the subject itself. The leading component of the content of teaching a foreign language is teaching various types of speech activity of speaking, listening, reading, writing. When teaching listening comprehension, each student gets the opportunity to hear foreign language speech. When teaching speaking, each student can say phrases in English into a microphone. When studying grammatical phenomena, each student can perform

grammatical exercises, has the opportunity to solve crosswords, chainwords, search for words, and perform game exercises.

In the practice of using a computer in the educational process, its teaching function is especially emphasized, and also, a computer is a tool that organizes and manages the independent work of students, especially in the process of training work with language and speech material.

The scope of the computer in teaching foreign languages is unusually wide. The computer can be effectively used to get acquainted with new language material, new patterns of statements, as well as with the activities of communication in a foreign language. At the training stage and at the stage of applying the formed knowledge, skills, abilities, the computer can be used in a wide variety of communicative tasks and situations, taking into account the personal characteristics of the trainees.

He can create optimal conditions for the successful mastering of the program material: at the same time, a flexible, sufficient and feasible load of exercises for all students in the class is provided. In addition, it is difficult to overestimate the role of the computer as a means of exercising control over the activities of students by the teacher, as well as a means of forming and improving self-control. In difficult cases, the computer allows the student to obtain the necessary information of a reference nature in a short period of time, to present him with certain "keys" for successfully solving the task.

An important feature of a computer in the teaching and upbringing process in a foreign language is that it can be a student's "interlocutor", that is, it can work in a communicatively oriented interactive mode and in a certain way, for example, with graphic tools, a speech analyzer and synthesizer, make up for the lack natural communicant, modeling and imitating his nonverbal and verbal behavior.

The computer allows you to present on the display screen elements of a country-specific nature, features of the environment and environment, which can be used as a background for the formation of students' speech activity in a foreign

language. The computer has great potential for constructing color images that can be transformed within the given limits.

The noted capabilities of the computer make it an excellent technical tool for various kinds of explanations and generalizations of the phenomena of language, speech, and speech activity.

Now in all schools there is an early teaching of foreign languages to students. Often in foreign language lessons, the process of involving students in oral speech on various topics is uninteresting. When working with the use of computers, this is impossible, since the visualization required in the lessons and the situations on the monitors are quite real - the "images" move, speak English, ask questions, etc. Some teachers may ask: won't the lesson turn from creative work into something entertaining? No, because in order to get a good grade when working with a computer, the student has to work creatively. He does everything with joy, and the teacher has to purchase the necessary electronic textbooks and make a selection of the necessary situations from them, as well as print out additional questions and texts and transfer them to all computers so that at a certain point in the lesson, students can sit down at certain computers, find and open desired folder in "My Documents", perform, for example, a listening or reading test. It's a lot of work, but it pays off. The joy of learning - that's what gives the use of computers in the classroom. And this, in turn, along with the development of thinking leads to the development of initiative speech. Each child has an internal motive aimed at cognitive activity. The task of the teacher is to contribute in every possible way to the development of this motive, not to let it fade away.

Now there is a wide variety of modern multimedia textbooks, where you can find enough exercises for students of all ages and different knowledge.

The program "Professor Higgins. English without an Accent" and also a number of other multimedia textbooks. Sounds, words, phrases and sentences are perceived by students by ear and visually. Students have the opportunity to observe articulation movements on the computer screen and perceive the correct intonation

by ear. At the same time, due to the rather high imitative abilities of students, the correct samples are imprinted in their memory.

The programs “Professor Higgins. English without an accent”, “English from A to Z”, “English. I and my family” To prepare for the exam, I use “English. Express preparation for the exam” and other training programs. A very interesting English language training program “Learn to learn” (national-regional component about the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)

The computerization of our society is calling for life and the emergence of more and more people who want and can use these smart machines in everyday life. Computers make life easier and more interesting. After all, if with the help of this machine within an hour or two you can attend training courses on the Internet in any subject of the school and extracurricular programs, see the world in its current state and diversity, communicate with a huge mass of different people and gain access to libraries, museums and exhibitions that one can only dream of, then there really is no better means for self-development and individual education and self-education.

The use of Internet resources and computer presentations in English lessons.

Now everyone understands that the Internet has colossal information capabilities and no less impressive services. The Internet creates a unique opportunity for foreign language learners to use authentic texts, listen and communicate with native speakers. It is important to decide for what purposes we are going to use its capabilities and resources. For example:

- to include the materials of the network in the content of the lesson,
- for students to independently search for information as part of the work on the project,

Using the information resources of the Internet, it is possible, by integrating them into the educational process, to more effectively solve a number of didactic tasks in the lesson:

- to form reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity,
- improve listening skills based on authentic Internet audio texts, also prepared by the teacher accordingly,
- to improve the skills of monologue and dialogic utterance on the basis of a problematic discussion of the network materials presented by the teacher or one of the students,
- replenish your vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language, reflecting a certain stage in the development of the culture of the people, the social and political structure of society,
- get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, especially the speech behavior of various peoples in terms of communication, cultural features, traditions of the country of the language being studied.

It is also optimal to create multimedia Power Point presentations. The use of computer presentations in the classroom allows you to introduce new lexical, country-specific material in the most exciting form, the principle of visibility is implemented, which contributes to a solid assimilation of information. Independent creative work of students to create computer presentations is the best way to expand the stock of active vocabulary.

The tasks of education modernization cannot be solved without the optimal implementation of information technologies in all its spheres. The use of information technology gives impetus to the development of new forms and content of traditional activities of students, which leads to their implementation at a higher level. Working with a computer should be organized in such a way that from the very first lessons of the initial stage of education it becomes a powerful psychological and pedagogical means of forming a need-motivational plan for the activity of schoolchildren, a means of maintaining and further developing their interest in the subject being studied. Properly organized work of students with a computer can contribute, in particular, to the growth of their cognitive and

communicative interest, which in turn will contribute to the activation and expansion of students' opportunities for independent work in mastering the English language, both in the classroom and outside of school hours.

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